

AN ANALYSIS OF NONLINEAR POST-BUCKLING FOR LAMINATED
COMPOSITE CYLINDRICAL SHELLS WITH INSIDE TRIANGULAR
ISOGRID STIFFENERS

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ABSTRACT

This paper makes use of the potential energy variation principle ¹ to analyze the post-buckling behavior of laminated composite cylindrical shells with inside grid stiffeners of equilateral triangles, in which the nonlinearities of both geometry and physics are considered. The influence of initial imperfection on post-buckling loads is studied for the cylindrical shell under compression. The nonlinear post-buckling equation is deduced by using Ritz's method. Finally, the numerical results are given for Glass/Epoxy and Carbon/Epoxy material with various laminations and compared with available experimental data.

INTRODUCTION

The stiffened cylindrical shell is a kind of efficient shell structure, which is often used in aeronautical engineering, astronautical engineering and civil engineering. The structural buckling is a main type of failure for stiffened cylindrical shells. Composite cylindrical shells of grid stiffeners is of increasingly important practical value for further improving the load-bearing capacity and raising the employable efficiency of shell structures. But, they also increase difficulty and complication of theoretical analysis. At present, it has become an important problem to find a method to analyze exactly grid-stiffened shells in theory and to obtain a numerical solution to the deduced governing equations.

In this paper, both the geometrical nonlinearity and marked material nonlinearity are taken into account to improve the precision of theoretical analysis. The nonlinear constitutive relation established by H.T.Hahn and S.W.Tsai ² shows that the physical nonlinearity of laminated composite shells is mainly reflected through shear effect. But for post-buckling problems, it is also very necessary to further consider the physical nonlinearity normal to the fibre orientation ³ because the stress level in the structure is often high.

In recent years, there are various methods used to treat the stiffness of stiffeners on stiffened shells. But, for stiffness treatment of grid stiffeners, they are often rough. Therefore, in the paper, the complete grid stiffeners are regarded as a space frame system, whose constitutive relation ⁴ can be obtained according to the grid configuration and material properties. The results obtained according to this kind of calculating model are quite satisfactory. Besides, the influence of initial imperfection of the practical structure on the buckling load of axial compression is taken into account in the analysis.

Finally, the numerical results are given for various lamination patterns of the cylindrical shell model of Glass/Epoxy and Carbon/Epoxy, and compared with available experimental data in this paper. It shows that the nonlinearities of physics and geometry have obvious influence on the buckling load of cylindrical shells and the magnitude of initial imperfect deflection will directly affect the magnitude of the critical load.

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

(1). Nonlinear Constitutive Equation of a Single-Layer Plate in Principal Axes

By calculating the variation of the refined Hahn-Tsai's relation, the nonlinear constitutive equation in critical buckling state may be expressed as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \delta \epsilon_1 \\ \delta \epsilon_2 \\ \delta \gamma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & 0 \\ S_{21} & S_{22} + 3S_{2222} \sigma_2^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S_{66} + 3S_{6666} \tau_{12}^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta \sigma_1 \\ \delta \sigma_2 \\ \delta \tau_{12} \end{Bmatrix}$$

or
$$= [S] \tag{1}$$

where S_{2222} and S_{6666} are the flexibility influence coefficients corresponding to lateral and shear physical nonlinearity, respectively. $[S]$ is a nonlinear flexibility matrix. By inverse operation of equation (1), the nonlinear constitutive equation in terms of stiffness can be obtained:

$$\{\delta \sigma\} = [\tilde{Q}]\{\delta \epsilon\} \tag{2}$$

where $[\tilde{Q}]$ is the nonlinear stiffness matrix.

(2). Nonlinear Geometry Equation

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \epsilon_x &= \frac{\partial \delta u_0}{\partial x} + \frac{\lambda}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 - z \frac{\partial^2 \delta w}{\partial x^2} \\ \delta \epsilon_y &= \frac{\partial \delta v_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\lambda}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \delta w}{\partial y} \right)^2 - \frac{\delta w}{R} - z \frac{\partial^2 \delta w}{\partial y^2} \\ \delta \gamma_{xy} &= \frac{\partial \delta u_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \delta v_0}{\partial x} + \lambda \frac{\partial \delta w}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{\partial \delta w}{\partial y} - 2z \frac{\partial^2 \delta w}{\partial x \partial y} \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where λ is Donnell's initial-imperfection factor, $\lambda = 1 + 2 \frac{w_0^*}{w}$.
 w_0^* is the amplitude of the initial-imperfection displacement.

(3) Constitutive Equation of Cylindrical Shell Structures

Assume that the angle included between the principal direction of the i -th lamina and the structural axis x is ϕ_i , and let $c = \cos \phi_i$, $s = \sin \phi_i$. By coordinate transformation, the constitutive relation in reference to the coordinate system of the structure may be expressed as⁵.

$$\{\delta \bar{\sigma}\}_i = [\bar{Q}]_i \{\delta \bar{\epsilon}\}_i \tag{4}$$

$$[\bar{Q}]_i = [T]^{-1} [\tilde{Q}]_i [R][T][R]^{-1} = [T]^{-1} [\tilde{Q}]_i [T]^{-T}$$

In hyper-matrix form, the relation between the internal force and strain of the structure can be derived:⁷

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \delta N \\ \delta M \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} A & B \\ B & D \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta \epsilon_0 \\ \delta \bar{\kappa} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

The total stiffness matrix of Equ.(5) consists of stiffness matrixes of the shell skin and the stiffeners, they are written respectively as:

$$\begin{aligned} [A] &= [A]_1 + [A'] = \sum_{i=1}^m [\bar{Q}]_i (z_i - z_{i-1}) + \begin{Bmatrix} A'_{11} & A'_{12} & A'_{16} \\ A'_{21} & A'_{22} & A'_{26} \\ A'_{61} & A'_{62} & A'_{66} \end{Bmatrix} \\ [B] &= [B]_1 + [B'] = \sum_{i=1}^m [\bar{Q}]_i (z_i^2 - z_{i-1}^2) + \begin{Bmatrix} B'_{11} & B'_{12} & B'_{16} \\ B'_{21} & B'_{22} & B'_{26} \\ B'_{61} & B'_{62} & B'_{66} \end{Bmatrix} \\ [D] &= [D]_1 + [D'] = \sum_{i=1}^m [\bar{Q}]_i (z_i^3 - z_{i-1}^3) + \begin{Bmatrix} D'_{11} & D'_{12} & D'_{16} \\ D'_{21} & D'_{22} & D'_{26} \\ D'_{61} & D'_{62} & D'_{66} \end{Bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

By reference 4, each stiffness coefficient of the stiffeners is:

$$\begin{aligned} A'_{ij} &= A'_{ji}, & A'_{11} &= \sum_{i=1}^n C_i c_i^4, & A'_{22} &= \sum_{i=1}^n C_i s_i^4, \\ A'_{12} &= A'_{66} = \sum_{i=1}^n C_i s_i^2 c_i^2, & A'_{16} &= \sum_{i=1}^n C_i s_i c_i^3, & A'_{26} &= \sum_{i=1}^n C_i s_i^3 c_i, \\ B'_{11} &= B'_{22} = B'_{12} = B'_{21} = \sum_{i=1}^n K_i s_i^2 c_i^2, & B'_{16} &= B'_{26} = \sum_{i=1}^n K_i s_i c_i \cos 2\theta, \\ B'_{61} &= B'_{62} = \sum_{i=1}^n K_i s_i c_i^3, & B'_{66} &= \sum_{i=1}^n K_i c_i^2 \cos 2\theta, \\ D'_{ij} &= D'_{ji}, & D'_{11} &= \sum_{i=1}^n I_i c_i^4, & D'_{22} &= \sum_{i=1}^n I_i s_i^4, \\ D'_{12} &= \frac{D'_{66}}{2} = \sum_{i=1}^n I_i s_i^2 c_i^2, & D'_{16} &= \sum_{i=1}^n I_i s_i c_i^3, & D'_{26} &= \sum_{i=1}^n I_i s_i^3 c_i. \end{aligned}$$

where

$$C_i = \frac{E_{ti} A_i}{L}, \quad K_i = \frac{G_i S_i}{L_i}, \quad I_i = \frac{E_{ti} J_i}{L_i},$$

$$s_i = \sin \theta_i, \quad c_i = \cos \theta_i,$$

n -- the number of typical grid stiffeners,
 θ_i -- the angle included between the i th stiffener and longitudinal axis (measured from x axis to y axis).

The substitution of the conditions in this paper gives the following formulas:

$$[A]=[A]_1+[A']=\sum_{i=1}^m [\bar{Q}]_i (z_i - z_{i-1}) + \frac{E_t A}{8L_1} \begin{pmatrix} 9 & 3 & 0 \\ 3 & 9 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 3 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$[B]=[B]_1+[B']=\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^m [\bar{Q}]_i (z_i^2 - z_{i-1}^2) + \frac{GS}{8L_1} \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 3 & 0 \\ 3 & 3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 6 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$[D]=[D]_1+[D']=\frac{1}{3} \sum_{i=1}^m [\bar{Q}]_i (z_i^3 - z_{i-1}^3) + \frac{E_1 J}{8L_1} \begin{pmatrix} 9 & 3 & 0 \\ 3 & 9 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 6 \end{pmatrix}$$

where E and G are the Young's modulus and shear modulus of stiffeners respectively. A, S and J are the cross sectional area, static moment and inertial moment of stiffeners. L₁ is the interval of stiffeness'. The half-inverse form of equation (5) is:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \delta \bar{\epsilon}_0 \\ \delta M \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a & -b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta N \\ \delta K \end{Bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

(4) Displacement Function and Stress Function

The compatible equation of the mid-plane may be derived as:

$$\begin{aligned} & a_{11} \frac{\partial^4 \delta F}{\partial y^4} + (2a_{12} + a_{66}) \frac{\partial^4 \delta F}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + a_{22} \frac{\partial^4 \delta F}{\partial x^4} - 2a_{16} \frac{\partial^4 \delta F}{\partial x \partial y^3} - 2a_{26} \frac{\partial^4 \delta F}{\partial x^3 \partial y} \\ & = \lambda \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 \delta w}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 - \frac{\partial^2 \delta w}{\partial x^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \delta w}{\partial y^2} \right] - \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial^2 \delta w}{\partial x^2} - (2b_{26} - b_{q1}) \frac{\partial^4 \delta w}{\partial x^3 \partial y} \\ & - (b_{21} \frac{\partial^4 \delta w}{\partial x^4} + b_{12} \frac{\partial^4 \delta w}{\partial y^4}) - (b_{11} + b_{22} - 2b_{66}) \frac{\partial^4 \delta w}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} - (2b_{16} - b_{D26}) \frac{\partial^4 \delta w}{\partial x \partial y^3} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

In consideration of the boundary conditions given and the practical wave pattern at buckling, we select the buckling displacement function of large deflection⁶ assumed by Karman-Qian, i.e.:

$$\delta w = f_0 + f_1 \sin \alpha x \sin \beta y + f_2 \sin^2 \alpha x \sin^2 \beta y \quad (9)$$

where, $\alpha = \frac{m\pi}{L}$; $\beta = \frac{n}{R}$; L-length of the shell; R-radius of the shell;

m-half-wave number in longitudinal direction;

n-wave number in circumferential direction.

Substituting equation (9) into equation (8), the stress function in terms of double trigonometric series may be obtained by comparing the bilateral coefficients of the equation:

$$\delta F = \frac{1}{4} \sum_{i=1}^{10} (F_i \cdot \cos k_i \alpha x \cos l_i \beta y + \bar{F}_i \cdot \sin k_i \alpha x \sin l_i \beta y) - \frac{1}{2} \bar{N}_x y^2 \quad (10)$$

where F_i and \bar{F}_i are functions of c_j, λ, f₁ and f₂. c_j (j=1-19) are functions of the elements a_{ij}, b_{ij} (i, j=1, 2, 6) of matrixes [a], [b] and parameters

$$\delta (= \frac{1}{L_x} = \frac{\alpha}{\beta}), \quad \xi (= \frac{1}{\delta})$$

(5) Total Potential Energy of the Structure

$$\begin{aligned} \pi &= U_1 + U_2 - W \\ &= \frac{1}{64} \alpha^2 \beta^2 \pi R L [(T_1 f_1^2 + T_2 f_2^2 + T_3 f_1^2 f_2 + T_4 f_2^3 + T_5 f_1^2 f_2^2 + T_6 f_1^4 + T_7 f_2^4) - \frac{4}{84} \bar{N}_x (4f_1^2 + 3f_2^2)] \\ &\quad + 2\pi R L \bar{N}_x^2 (\bar{A}_{11} - a_{11}). \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where U_1 and U_2 are strain energy of the shell skin and the grid stiffeners, respectively. Therefore, total strain energy U may be written as:

$$U = U_1 + U_2 = \frac{1}{2} (2\pi R) \int_0^L (\{\delta N\}^T [\bar{A}] \{\delta N\} + \{\delta N\}^T [\bar{B}] \{\delta k\} + \{\delta k\}^T [\bar{D}] \{\delta k\}) dx dy \quad (12)$$

$$[\bar{A}] = [\bar{A}]_1 + [\bar{A}]_2, \quad [\bar{B}] = [\bar{B}]_1 + [B]_2, \quad [\bar{D}] = [\bar{D}]_1 + [\bar{D}]_2$$

$$[\bar{A}]_1 = [a][A]_1[a], \quad [\bar{B}]_1 = 2[a][B]_1 - 2[a][A]_1[b],$$

$$[\bar{D}]_1 = [b]^T [A]_1 [b] - 2[B]_1 [b] + [D]_1$$

$$[\bar{A}]_2 = \frac{E_t A}{L_1} [a]^T [\bar{\theta}] [a], \quad [\bar{B}]_2 = \frac{4E_t S}{L_1} [a]^T [\bar{\theta}] + \frac{4E_t A}{L_1} [a]^T [\bar{\theta}] [b],$$

$$[\bar{D}]_2 = \frac{2E_t J}{L_1} [\bar{\theta}] - \frac{4E_t S}{L_1} [\bar{\theta}] [b] + \frac{2E_t A}{L_1} [b]^T [\bar{\theta}] [b]$$

$$[\bar{\theta}] = \sum_{i=1}^3 [\theta]_i = \frac{1}{8} \begin{bmatrix} 9 & 3 & 0 \\ 3 & 9 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

work done by the axial force \bar{N}_x of cylindrical shell in the axial contraction ΔL is:

$$W = 2\pi R \bar{N}_x \Delta L = \frac{1}{16} \lambda \pi R \alpha^2 L \bar{N}_x (4f_1^2 + 3f_2^2) + 2\pi R L a_{11} \bar{N}_x^2 \quad (13)$$

(6) Nonlinear Post-Buckling Equation and its Solving Process

The relation between deflecting parameters can be obtained by inextensional condition of the mid-surface perimeter, i.e.:

$$f_0 = a_{12} R \bar{N}_x + \frac{\lambda}{32} \beta^2 R (4f_1^2 + 3f_2^2) - \frac{1}{4} f_2 \quad (14)$$

According to Ritz's method, two simultaneous nonlinear algebraic equations may be derived:

$$f_1^2 = \frac{[(1.5T_1 - 2T_2) + (1.5T_3 - 3T_4)f_2 + (1.5T_5 - 4T_7)f_2^2]f_2}{[T_3 + 2T_5 - 3T_6]f_2} \quad (15)$$

$$\bar{N}_k = \frac{\beta^2}{16\lambda} (T_1 + T_3 f_2 + T_5 f_2^2 + 2T_6 f_1^2)$$

By programming and iterative computation, the critical axial compression \bar{N}_{xc} and value f_1 corresponding to different wave numbers m, n and different value f_2 and satisfying convergence condition can be solved. For detailed derivation see Ref. 8.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLE AND CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, several different layups of grid-stiffened cylinder made of G./E. and C./E. material are calculated numerically according to the geometrical model of available experimental samples. In the calculation, the classical small deflection buckling, the geometrical nonlinearity buckling, the geometrical and physical nonlinearity buckling and the buckling including or excluding initial imperfection are taken into account respectively. The numerical results are compared with the available experimental data.

The material and geometry data used in this paper are as follows.

(1) Glass/Epoxy material

$$E_1 = 4090(\text{kg/mm}^2), \quad E_2 = 885(\text{kg/mm}^2), \quad G_{12} = 651(\text{kg/mm}^2)$$

$$\mu = 0.31, \quad S_{2222} = 1.672 \times 10^{-6}(\text{kg/mm}^2)^{-3}, \quad S_{6666} = 7.558 \times 10^{-5}(\text{kg/mm}^2)^{-3}$$

(2) Carbon/Epoxy material

$$E_1 = 11800(\text{kg/mm}^2), \quad E_2 = 950(\text{kg/mm}^2), \quad G_{12} = 620(\text{kg/mm}^2)$$

$$\mu = 0.31, \quad S_{2222} = 6.17 \times 10^{-7}(\text{kg/mm}^2)^{-3}, \quad S_{6666} = 1.054 \times 10^{-4}(\text{kg/mm}^2)^{-3}$$

(3) Geometrical demensions of the stiffened cylinder:

Radius of the cylinder $R=300\text{mm}$. Length of the cylinder $L=345\text{mm}$.

Thickness of the cylindrical skin $h=1.50\text{mm}$ (average value).

Side-length of the triangular stiffener $l=43.5\text{mm}$.

Height of the stiffener $H=3.51\text{mm}$. Width of the stiffener $b=2.00\text{mm}$. To examine the theoretical analysis and calculation method of this paper, four G./E. experimental samples with experimental results available are calculated first. Their practical layups are $[90^\circ, +30^\circ, -30^\circ]$, $h_{90}=0.7\text{mm}$, $h_{+30}=0.45\text{mm}$, $h_{-30}=0.45\text{mm}$.

The average value of experimental buckling loads is $337.5(\text{KN})$, i.e., $34.4(\text{T})$. The nonlinear buckling load calculated for this model is $363(\text{KN})$, i.e., $37(\text{T})$. It can be judged that the two loads are in good agreement. The theoretical analysis method and calculated results presented in this paper are of much value for reference.

For a further research into the layup regularity, the variation of the critical buckling load of the same G./E. cylinder aforementioned is obtained by varying its thickness and layup, as shown in Table (1).

Table (1)

thickness of cylindrical skin	1.50(mm)	1.60(mm)	1.60(mm)	1.60(mm)
layup	$[30^\circ, -30^\circ, 0^\circ]$	$[30^\circ, -30^\circ, 90^\circ, 90^\circ, -30^\circ, 30^\circ]$	$[30^\circ, -30^\circ, 0^\circ, 0^\circ, -30^\circ, 30^\circ]$	$[30^\circ / -30^\circ]_3$
thickness of single layer	equal thickness	equal thickness	equal thickness	equal thickness
buckling load	66.64(T)	58.39(T)	111.97(T)	241.93(T)

To show the influence of nonlinearity on buckling loads, the classical

small deflection buckling and the post-buckling of C./E. cylinder (L=600mm) are calculated and compared respectively for different thicknesses of cylindrical skin and layup, as shown in Table (2).

Table (2)

thickness of cylindrical skin	2.10(mm)	1.40(mm)	0.90(mm)
layup	[90°, -30°, 30°, 0°] 30°, -30°, 90°]	[90°, -30°, 30°, 0°] 30°, -30°, 90°]	[30°, -30°, 0°]
linear buckling	145.89 (T)	94.62 (T)	75.40 (T)
non-linear buckling	102.90 (T)	62.77 (T)	53.90 (T)

To show the influence of initial imperfection on the buckling loads, calculations are made for the G./E. and C./E. cylinders under a series of different initial imperfection factor λ . The results are shown in Fig. (1) and Fig.(2), respectively.

Figs. (1) and (2) The nonlinear buckling curve of G./E. and C./E. cylinder under different λ

These results show:

1. It can be obtained from Table (1) that the influence of layup on buckling loads is obvious. Increasing the filament quantity in load direction or the number of layers is an important method by which the buckling loads are improved. If the layup can be such as to get a solution close to an orthotropic solution, a considerable increase in buckling loads would result.
2. It is shown in Figs. (1) and (2) that cylindrical shells of both materials are markedly affected by the initial imperfection. Their buckling loads decrease with the increasing imperfection factor λ . Although the sensitivity of the stiffened shell is lower than that of a smooth shell, the composite cylindrical shell is still sensitive to initial imperfections, and it is highly dependent on the layup pattern.
3. It can also be seen from Tab. (2) that under equal conditions, the buckling load by classical small-deflection theory differs considerably from that obtained by including nonlinearities and initial imperfections. The former results are not safe enough for practical use, while the latter ones are more close to reality. Therefore, the effect of the two nonlinearities can not be ignored in theoretical analysis, especially for composite shell structures.
4. To sum up, the energy-semi analytical method presented in this paper with its effective treatment of the grid stiffener here is relatively rigorous and yields rather satisfactory results. When run on computers, the method has the advantages of easy programming, less time, lower cost,

and feasibility on microcomputers. Capable of solving rather complex practical structural problems by fairly simple algorithm, the method is of much practical value.

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